

OPTIMAL DESIGN OF ANISOTROPIC (FIBER-REINFORCED) FLYWHEELS

R.M. Christensen
and
E.M. Wu

Lawrence Livermore Laboratory, University of California
Livermore, California 94550

An analysis is given of the kinetic energy storage capacity of anisotropic flywheels. Using a uniform strain failure criteria, the optimal shapes of flywheels are determined as a function of the degree of anisotropy. Within this spectrum of shapes, practical design considerations are shown to favor the case where there is equal reinforcement in the radial and circumferential directions. Comparisons are made between the present solid-wheel-type design and the ring design.